

GLOBAL SENSITIVITY AND UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF ASYMMETRIC BISTABLE ENERGY HARVESTERS

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Abstract. This study investigates the performance of asymmetric bistable energy harvesters with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling, focusing on the impact of parametric variability on system reliability. Global sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices identifies critical parameters influencing harvested power, providing insights for the robust design of nonlinear harvesters. To address uncertainties in system parameters, we employ a probabilistic framework incorporating Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) and probabilistic maps. This approach, leveraging the maximum entropy principle, models and propagates uncertainties to visualize their effects on power output. Results show that excitation frequency, amplitude, asymmetric terms, and piezoelectric coupling properties are critical factors, with their importance varying across dynamic stability regimes. Our findings highlight the need to account for joint parameter variability to enhance energy harvesting system efficiency and reliability.

Keywords: Energy harvesting; Nonlinear dynamics; Asymmetric system; Sensitivity analysis; Sobol' indices; Uncertainty quantification

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy harvesting from environmental vibrations has gained significant attention as a means to power autonomous devices. Among the various energy harvesting mechanisms, bistable systems have shown enhanced performance due to their ability to exploit nonlinearities, thereby increasing energy capture across a broad frequency range [1, 2, 3]. However, such systems are highly sensitive to parametric uncertainties and geometric imperfections, which can affect their performance and reliability [4].

This study focuses on the global sensitivity analysis (GSA) and uncertainty quantification (UQ) of an asymmetric bistable energy harvester with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling [5, 6]. The sensitivity analysis approach employs Sobol indices, computed via Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE), to quantify the influence of each parameter on the harvested power, providing a basis for optimizing harvester design under uncertainty.

But while GSA provides valuable insights, it does not explain how these parameters affect power harvesting under uncertainty. To address this gap, this paper integrates a parametric probabilistic approach [7] to model and quantify these impacts, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how uncertainties affect the system response.

2 MATHEMATICAL MODELING

The asymmetric bistable energy harvester under consideration, Figure 1, is modeled by the following set of nonlinear differential equations:

$$\ddot{x} + 2\xi\dot{x} - \frac{1}{2}x(1-x^2) - (1 + \beta|x|)\chi v = f \cos(\Omega t) + p \sin \phi, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{v} + \lambda v + (1 + \beta|x|)\kappa \dot{x} = 0, \quad (2)$$

where x denotes the beam tip displacement, v is the voltage across the resistive circuit, ξ represents the damping ratio, χ and κ are piezoelectric coupling coefficients, λ is a time constant, f is the excitation amplitude, Ω is the excitation frequency, ϕ is the bias angle, and β characterizes the nonlinear piezoelectric coupling.

Figure 1: Asymmetric bistable energy harvester with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling.

The quantity of interest (QoI) is the mean output power, given by

$$P = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} \lambda v(t)^2 dt. \quad (3)$$

To model the parametric uncertainties, we employ a probabilistic approach based on the maximum entropy principle, which ensures the least biased estimation for the probability distributions given the limited information available. Since the only known information for the random variables (such as excitation frequency, amplitude, and material properties) is their range of possible values (support), the maximum entropy principle yields uniform distributions for each parameter. These distributions are assumed to be independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) due to the lack of any known correlations between the parameters.

The propagation of uncertainties through the system is performed using a Monte Carlo simulation [8], which is efficiently approximated by a PCE surrogate model. The PCE provides an accurate and computationally efficient way to estimate the system’s response to random variations in parameters, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the effects of uncertainty on power output.

Sobol indices are employed for global sensitivity analysis to quantify the contribution of each input parameter to the variance of the model output. Rather than using a direct Monte Carlo simulation, which can be computationally expensive, we compute these indices more efficiently through PCE. PCE expresses the model output as a series of orthogonal polynomials in terms of the input random variables, with each polynomial term having an associated coefficient that indicates its contribution to the output. The Sobol indices are then directly derived from these PCE coefficients. The first-order Sobol index, which measures the variance contribution of a single parameter, is calculated by summing the squared PCE coefficients related to that parameter. Higher-order Sobol indices, which account for the interactions between multiple parameters, are similarly obtained by summing the squared coefficients corresponding to the polynomial terms involving those parameters. This method significantly reduces computational costs by leveraging the PCE surrogate model, which provides an accurate approximation of the original model, facilitating efficient variance decomposition and sensitivity analysis.

All the simulations reported here were done with the package STONEHENGE - Suite for Nonlinear Analysis of Energy Harvesting Systems [9], which has modules for UQ and GSA.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model parameters analyzed include the damping ratio ($\xi = 0.01$), the electrical coupling constant ($\kappa = 0.5$), the time constant reciprocal ($\lambda = 0.05$), the nonlinear coupling coefficient ($\beta = 1$), the quadratic nonlinearity coefficient ($\delta = 0.15$), and the excitation frequency ($\Omega = 0.8$). The bias angle (ϕ) was set to 10° , while the excitation amplitude (f) is varied to explore different types of dynamic oscillations such as intrawell, interwell, and chaotic motions. The adopted initial condition is $(x_0, \dot{x}_0, v_0) = (1, 0, 0)$.

3.1 Key sensitivity findings

Figure 2 illustrates the variation of Sobol indices with respect to the amplitude of excitation for an asymmetric bistable energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The Sobol indices indicate the contribution of each input parameter to the variance in harvested power, providing insight into how different parameters affect power output across various excitation amplitudes.

The results reveal that for configurations with high excitation amplitudes, the electrical coupling parameter (κ) predominantly influences power output, particularly in regimes characterized by interwell motion. The excitation frequency (Ω) and amplitude (f) are critical in enhancing power in intrawell and chaotic motion regimes, respectively. Furthermore, for low and medium amplitudes of excitation, the bias angle (ϕ) significantly impact system behavior. These findings underscore the importance of considering parameter interactions to optimize energy harvesting performance. For a deeper analysis of bistable energy harvesting systems with Sobol indices, the reader is referred to [5].

Figure 2: Variation of the Sobol indices with respect to the amplitude of excitation for the asymmetric bistable energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The Sobol indices quantify the contribution of each input parameter to the variance in the harvested power, illustrating how different parameters influence power output across various excitation amplitudes.

3.2 Impact of uncertainty quantification

To further explore the influence of parametric variability, we integrated uncertainty quantification methodologies, including the PCE surrogate model, to construct probabilistic maps. These maps, shown in Figure 3, illustrate the conditional probability of increasing the nominal mean power by 50% when each parameter is increased by 10%, plotted against the excitation amplitude for the asymmetric energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The maps reveal that the excitation parameters (Ω and f) and the piezoelectric coupling terms (κ and β) are the most sensitive, with significant variability in harvested power across different stability regimes.

The analysis confirms that excitation frequency and amplitude are pivotal in enhancing power in intrawell and chaotic motion regimes, respectively. Meanwhile, piezoelectric coupling parameters play a crucial role in interwell motions. These results demonstrate the importance of understanding parametric uncertainties to achieve robust and optimized designs for nonlinear energy harvesters. For a more comprehensive examination of the uncertainty quantification, the reader is invited to consult [6].

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a robust framework for understanding the effects of uncertainties in bistable energy harvesting systems with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling and geometric asymmetries. The results emphasize the critical role of excitation frequency, amplitude, and piezoelectric properties in determining power output under varying dynamic conditions. These insights can guide the design and optimization of more reliable and efficient energy harvesters [10]. Future research could extend this approach to explore other forms of nonlinearities or consider multi-physics couplings to further enhance the robustness and performance of energy harvesting devices.

Figure 3: Conditional probability of increasing the nominal mean power by 50% as each parameter is increased by 10%, plotted against the excitation amplitude for the asymmetric energy harvester model with nonlinear piezoelectric coupling. The graph highlights the relative importance of each parameter in improving energy harvesting performance under different excitation conditions.

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